

L (δ^* -OPEN, OPEN) MAPPINGS

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Abstract: By using δ^* -open sets of Singal and Yadav [14], we introduce the concept of L (δ^* -open, open) mappings, named as nomenclature of mappings mentioned in paper [5]. This new class of L (δ^* -open, open) mappings is a super class of strongly continuous mappings of Levine [6] and a subclass of the class of strongly θ -continuous mappings of Noiri [11] as well as that of super continuous mappings of Munshi and Bassan [10]. L (δ^* -open, open) mappings are shown as independent of strongly semicontinuous mappings due to yadav [16]. Various characterizations and some preservation properties of the new mappings are investigated.

Key words: δ -open, δ^* -open sets; strongly continuous, strongly semicontinuous, L (δ^* -open, open), super continuous and strongly θ -continuous mappings.

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1. Introduction

In 1960, Levine [6] introduced the concept of strongly continuous mappings in topological spaces and obtained their properties. In 1963, Levine [7] introduced the notion of semi-open sets as a generalization of open sets. In 1966, Velico [13] introduced the concepts of θ -open and δ -open sets and obtained their properties. In 1974, Arya and Gupta [1] introduced completely continuous mappings and obtained their characterizations. In 1980, by using θ -open sets, Noiri [11] introduced strongly θ -continuous mappings. In 1981, Jain [4] introduced the concepts of totally continuous mappings. In 1982, Munshi and Bassan [10] introduced the notion of super continuous mappings. In 1987, Singal and Yadav [14] introduced a weak form of δ -open set is called δ^* -open set. In 1988, Yadav [16] introduced the notion of strongly semi-continuous mappings. In 1990, Popa [12] introduced the concept of almost feebly continuous functions and obtained their properties.

2. Preliminaries

A subset G of a space X is defined as **δ -open** [13] if for each $x \in G$, there exists a regular open set H such that $x \in H \subset G$. Similarly, Singal and Yadav [14] defined $G \subset X$ to be **δ^* -open** if for each $x \in G$, there exists a clopen set H such that $x \in H \subset G$. A set A is **δ^* -closed** (resp. **δ -closed**) iff $X - A$ is δ^* -open (resp. δ -open) and (**δ^* -clopen** if it is both δ^* -open and δ^* -closed). The collection of all δ^* -open sets in a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , denoted by **δ^* -O(X, \mathfrak{T})**, is a topology \mathfrak{T}^* on X , called **O-dimensionalization** [14] of \mathfrak{T} . They further showed that $\mathfrak{T} = \mathfrak{T}^*$

iff the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a O -dimensional space. $A \subset X$ is said to be **semiopen** [7] (resp. **feebly-open** [9]) if $G \subset A \subset \text{cl}(G)$, (resp. $G \subset A \subset \text{s-cl}(G)$), where s-cl denotes semiclosure for some open set G . A is called **θ -open** [13] if for each $x \in A$, there exists an open set G such that $x \in G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset A$. Obviously, every δ^* -open set is δ -open as well as θ -open. However, in $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ is δ -open but not δ^* -open and in the usual space of reals an open interval (a, b) is θ -open but not δ^* -open. The smallest δ^* -closed set containing A is called **δ^* -closure** of A denoted by **$\delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$** , and the largest δ^* -open set in A is called **δ^* -interior** of A , denoted by **$\delta^*\text{-int}(A)$** . A is δ^* -closed (resp. δ^* -open) iff $A = \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$ (resp. $A = \delta^*\text{-int}(A)$). Making use of δ^* -open sets, we introduce a new class of mappings called L (δ^* -open, open) mapping. This new class of mappings contains the class of strongly continuous mappings [6] properly and is contained in the classes of strongly θ -continuous mappings [11] as well as super continuous mappings [10].

3. Definitions and characterizations

3.1 Definition. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **L (δ^* -open, open)** at $x \in X$, if to every open set M containing $f(x)$, there exists a δ^* -open set N containing x such that $f(N) \subset M$. f is said to be **L (δ^* -open, open)** if it is **L (δ^* -open, open)** at each $x \in X$.

3.2 Definition. A set $G \subset X$, is said to be **δ^* -open neighborhood** [14] of $x \in X$, if there exists a δ^* -open set H such that $x \in H \subset G$.

3.3 Theorem. For a mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$, the following are equivalent:

- f is **L (δ^* -open, open)**.
- Inverse images of every open set is δ^* -open. i. e. f is **I (δ^* -open, open)**.
- Inverse image of every closed set is δ^* -closed i.e. f is **I (δ^* -closed, closed)**.
- $f(\delta^*\text{-cl}(A)) \subset \text{cl}(f(A))$ for each subset A of X .
- $\delta^*\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(B)) \subset f^{-1}(\text{cl}(B))$ for each subset B of Y .
- For each point x of X and for each neighborhood M of $f(x)$, there exists a δ^* -open neighborhood N of x such that $f(N) \subset M$.

Proof. The proof is easy to establish.

3.4 Theorem. For a bijection $f : X \rightarrow Y$, the following are equivalents:

- f is **L (δ^* -open, open)**
- $\text{Int}(f(A)) \subset f(\delta^*\text{-int}(A))$ for each subset A of X .
- $f^{-1}(\text{int}(B)) \subset \delta^*\text{-int}(f^{-1}(B))$ for each subset B of Y .

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b). For each subset A of X , $\text{int}(f(A)) \subset f(A) \Rightarrow f^{-1}(\text{int}(f(A))) \subset A \Rightarrow \delta^*\text{-int}(f^{-1}(\text{int}(f(A)))) \subset \delta^*\text{-int}(A)$ or $f^{-1}(\text{int}(f(A))) \subset \delta^*\text{-int}(A)$. Thus, $\text{int}(f(A)) \subset f(\delta^*\text{-int}(A))$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). For $B \subset Y$, $f^{-1}(B) \subset X$, so, $\text{int}(f(f^{-1}(B))) \subset f(\delta^*\text{-int}(f^{-1}(B)))$ or, $\text{int}(B) \subset f(\delta^*\text{-int}(f^{-1}(B)))$ or, $f^{-1}(\text{int}(B)) \subset \delta^*\text{-int}(f^{-1}(B))$.

(c) \Rightarrow (a). If A is open in Y , then, $f^{-1}(\text{int}(A)) \subset \delta^*\text{-int}(f^{-1}(A)) \Rightarrow A \subset f(\delta^*\text{-int}(f^{-1}(A))) \Rightarrow f^{-1}(A) \subset \delta^*\text{-int}(f^{-1}(A))$. Thus $f^{-1}(A)$ is δ^* -open.

Singal and Yadav [14] have shown that the collection of all clopen sets in a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) forms a base for a topology \mathfrak{T}^* and A is \mathfrak{T}^* -open iff A is δ^* -open in (X, \mathfrak{T}) . The subtopology \mathfrak{T}^* is called **O-dimensionalization** [14] of \mathfrak{T} . Also, a space is O-dimensional iff $\mathfrak{T} = \mathfrak{T}^*$. Using this, we have

3.5 Theorem. For a mapping $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow Y$, the following are equivalent:

- (a) f is L (δ^* -open, open).
- (b) $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}^*) \rightarrow Y$ is continuous.
- (c) f is continuous provided X is O-dimensional.

Proof. Obvious.

4. Comparisons

4.1 Definition. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **super continuous** [10] (resp. **Completely continuous** [1], **totally continuous** [4], **strongly θ -continuous** [11]) if inverse image of every open set in Y is δ -open (resp. regular open, clopen, θ -open) set in X ,

Since every δ^* -open set is δ -open, so every L (δ^* -open, open) mapping is super continuous but the converse is not true as shown in the following example:

4.2 Example. If $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the identity map on (X, \mathfrak{T}) is super continuous but not L (δ^* -open, open).

Singal and Yadav [14] have shown that every regular open set is clopen in an extremally disconnected space. So we conclude that every δ -open set is δ^* -open in an extremally disconnected space and hence every super continuous (or completely continuous) mapping on an extremally disconnected space is L (δ^* -open, open).

The following example shows the necessity of extremally disconnectedness of the domain space.

4.3 Example. Let $X = \{p, q, r, s\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{p\}, \{q, r\}, \{p, q, r\}\}$, and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\psi = \{\phi, Y, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Then $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \psi)$ defined by $f(p) = b$, $f(q) = a = f(r)$, $f(s) = b$ is completely continuous and hence super continuous but not L (δ^* -open, open).

Moreover, every δ^* -open set is θ -open, therefore, every L (δ^* -open, open) mapping is strongly θ -continuous but the converse is not true in general, as following example shows.

4.4 Example. The identity map on the real line \mathbb{R} is strongly θ -continuous but not $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

Since closure of an open set is open in an extremally disconnected space, so every θ -open set is δ^* -open and hence every strongly θ -continuous mapping on an extremally disconnected space is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

4.5 Definiton. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **strongly continuous** [6] (resp. **strongly semicontinuous** [16]) if $f(\text{cl}(A)) \subset f(A)$ (resp. $f(\text{s-cl}(A)) \subset f(A)$) for every subset A of X .

Obviously, every strongly continuous map is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) but the converse is true provided the domain space is discrete, otherwise, the following example.

4.6 Example. If $X = \{a, b\}$ with indiscrete topology on X , then the identity map on X is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) but not strongly continuous.

The mappings being $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) and being strongly semicontinuous are independent concepts as the following example shows:

4.7 Example [16]. Let X be the set of reals with the usual topology and let $Y = \{a, b\}$ with discrete topology. The map $f : X \rightarrow Y$ defined by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } -\infty < x < 0 \\ b & \text{if } 0 < x < \infty \end{cases}$$

is strongly semicontinuous but not $L(\delta^*$ -open, open). The $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) mapping discussed in **Example 4.6** is not even strongly semi-continuous.

The following example shows that even a homeomorphism may fail to be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

4.8 Example. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{y\}, \{z\}, \{y, z\}\}$. Then the identity map on (X, \mathfrak{T}) is homeomorphism but not $L(\delta^*$ -open, open). It also shows that a bijective η -continuous map carrying δ -open (resp. δ -closed) sets on to δ -open (resp. δ -closed) sets may fail to be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

Thus we have the following Implication diagram:

Where, \rightarrow indicates implies but not implied by and \leftrightarrow indicates independence.

5. Properties of $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) mappings

5.1 Theorem.

- (a) Every constant map is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).
- (b) Every mapping with domain a discrete space is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).
- (c) Every mapping with codomain an indiscrete space is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).
- (d) If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) then it remains so if the topology on X is replaced by a finer topology and / or the topology on Y is replaced by a coarser topology.

5.2 Definition. A mapping is said to be **S-continuous** [15] (resp. **semi continuous** [7], **slightly semicontinuous** [14], **feeble continuous** [3], **almost feeble continuous** [12], **faintly continuous** [8]) iff inverse image of every semiopen (resp. open, clopen, open, δ -open, θ -open) set is open (resp. semiopen, semiopen, feebly open, α -open (or feebly open) open) set respectively.

5.3 Definition. A mapping is said to be **D(δ^* -open, δ -open)** (resp. **D(δ^* -closed, δ -closed)**) if it maps δ^* -open (resp. δ^* -closed) sets on to δ -open (resp. δ -closed) sets.

5.4 Theorem. Regarding composite mappings, the following are easy to establish.

For $f : X \rightarrow Y$, and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$, $g \circ f$ is

- (a) $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) whenever f is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) and g is continuous.
- (b) Semicontinuous whenever f is slightly semicontinuous and g is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

5.5 Theorem.

- (a) If $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ is an open map, $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) then $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).
- (b) If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) and $D(\delta^*$ -open, open) map and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ then $g \circ f$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) iff g is $L(\delta$ -open, open).
- (c) Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) surjection and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$. If $g \circ f$ is $D(\delta^*$ -open, δ -open), (or $D(\delta^*$ -closed, δ -closed)) so is g .
- (d) Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) injection. If $g \circ f$ is $D(\delta^*$ -open, δ -open) (or $D(\delta^*$ -closed, δ -closed)) so is f .

5.6 Corollary.

- (a) Composition of two $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) mappings is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).
- (b) If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is faintly continuous, $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) then $g \circ f$ is continuous.
- (c) If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost feeble continuous and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open), then $g \circ f$ is feeble continuous.

5.7 Theorem.

 Restriction of an $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) map is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

Proof. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open). $A \subset X$, $f_A : A \rightarrow Y$, Let G be open in Y , then $f^{-1}(G)$ is δ^* -open in X . To show $f_A^{-1}(G) = f^{-1}(G) \cap A$, δ^* -open in A . If $x \in f_A^{-1}(G)$, then there exists a clopen set H such that $x \in H \subset f^{-1}(G)$ and hence $x \in (H \cap A) \subset f_A^{-1}(G)$ showing $f_A^{-1}(G)$ is δ^* -open in A .

5.8 Theorem. Let $X = A \cup B$, where A and B are clopen sets in X . Let $f : A \rightarrow Y$ and $g : B \rightarrow Y$ be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open). If $f(x) = g(x)$ for every x in $A \cap B$, then $h : X \rightarrow Y$ defined by $h(x) = f(x)$ if x in A and $h(x) = g(x)$ if x is in B , is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

Proof. Let G be open in Y . Then $h^{-1}(G) = f^{-1}(G) \cup g^{-1}(G)$ is δ^* -open in X as both $f^{-1}(G)$ and $g^{-1}(G)$ are δ^* -open in clopen sets A and B respectively and hence δ^* -open in X .

5.9 Corollary.

(a) Let $X = \cup \{A_\lambda : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$, where A_λ 's are clopen and pairwise disjoint and $f_\lambda : A_\lambda \rightarrow Y$ be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) for each λ . Then $h : X \rightarrow Y$ defined by $h(x) = f_\lambda(x)$ if $x \in A_\lambda$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

(b) Let $X = \cup X_i$ where X_i 's are clopen sets in X . Then $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) iff the restriction f_{X_i} is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) for each i .

5.10 Theorem. If the graph map $g : X \rightarrow X \times Y$ of $f : X \rightarrow Y$ defined by $g(x) = (x, f(x))$ for each $x \in X$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) then so is f .

Proof. If $x \in X$ and V is any open set containing $f(x)$ then $X \times V$ is open in $X \times Y$ containing $(x, f(x))$, so, there exists a δ^* -open set U in X , such that $g(U) \subset X \times V$. hence $f(U) \subset V$.

5.11 Theorem. Let $f_1 : X_1 \rightarrow Y_1$ and $f_2 : X_2 \rightarrow Y_2$ be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) maps. If $X = X_1 \times X_2$, $Y = Y_1 \times Y_2$ then $f : X \rightarrow Y$ defined by $f(x_1, x_2) = (f_1(x_1), f_2(x_2))$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open).

Proof. Let G_1 be open in Y_1 and G_2 be open in Y_2 . Then $G_1 \times G_2$ is basic open in Y and hence $f_1^{-1}(G_1) \times f_2^{-1}(G_2)$ is δ^* -open in X .

5.12 Corollary. Let $\{X_\lambda : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$ and $\{Y_\lambda : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$ be two families of topological spaces. If $f_\lambda : X_\lambda \rightarrow Y_\lambda$ is L (δ^* -open, open) then the map $f : \prod X_\lambda \rightarrow \prod Y_\lambda$ defined by $f(\{x_\lambda\}) = \{f_\lambda(x_\lambda)\}$ is L (δ^* -open, open) for each λ .

5.13 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow \prod X_\lambda$ is L (δ^* -open, open) then $P_\lambda \circ f : X \rightarrow X_\lambda$ is L (δ^* -open, open) and conversely where P_λ is λ th projection.

Proof. Since all projections are continuous, so the composition map $P_\lambda \circ f$ is L (δ^* -open, open). Conversely, if $G = p_\lambda^{-1}(U)$ for some λ is any member of the defining subbase for the product space, then $f^{-1}(G) = f^{-1}(p_\lambda^{-1}(U)) = (p_\lambda \circ f)^{-1}(U)$ is δ^* -open in X .

5.14 Theorem. A map $f : X \rightarrow (Y, U)$ is L (δ^* -open, open) iff $f : X \rightarrow (f(X), U_{f(X)})$ is L (δ^* -open, open) where $U_{f(X)}$ is relativization of U to $f(X)$.

Proof. If H is open in $U_{f(X)}$ then $H = G \cap f(X)$ for some open set G in (Y, U) and $f^{-1}(H) = f^{-1}(G) \cap f(X)$ is δ^* -open in X . The converse is obvious.

5.15 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be L (δ^* -open, open). If Z is a space having Y as a subspace then the map $h : X \rightarrow Z$ is L (δ^* -open, open).

Proof. Let S be open in Z and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be the inclusion map. Then $g^{-1}(S)$ is open in Y and $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(S)) = (g \circ f)^{-1}(S) = h^{-1}(S)$ is δ^* -open.

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